

PERFECT HUMAN EDUCATION IN THE WORK OF OTKIR**HASHIMOV****Kimyoxon Andakulova**

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Abstract: The main goal of literature is to convey the concept of spirituality to the mind of the student in literature classes, to shape and develop his human feelings, in a word, to educate today's "Perfect Man". Therefore, by showing the way of the life and creativity of its creators, by studying and commenting on their works, by inculcating the content of the work and the concepts of humanity in the work, inculcating concepts such as love, consequences, love for the country, conscience and faith to the reader, see how relevant the topic is. shows.

Key words: literature, methodology, Perfect person, O'tkir Hashimov.

Developments and changes in the current era of globalization, like any other field, place great tasks on the field of literature. First of all, in literature lessons, the main goal of the literature field is to convey the concept of spirituality to the student's mind, to shape and develop his human feelings, in a word, to educate today's "Perfect Man". Therefore, by showing the way of the life and creativity of its creators, by studying and commenting on their works, by inculcating the content of the work and the concepts of humanity in the work, inculcating concepts such as love, consequences, love for the country, conscience and faith to the reader, see how relevant the topic is. shows. O'tkir Hashimov is one of the most popular and beloved writers of the Uzbek people. Many short stories of the writer, such as "Spring does not return", "Listen to your heart", "There is light, there is shadow", "Works of the world", "Between two doors", "Lifetimes spent in a dream", "Two times two to five", stories, novels are works that are in the heart of our people.

They reflect the problems of the time and their consequences are described very convincingly. Especially among them, the novel "Tushda khechgan umlar" written after we gained independence, has a special place. In this novel, under the guise of "fighting against bribery and putting an end to it" by the center, under the guise of "fighting against bribery and putting an end to it", under the guise of "fighting against bribery" and "Uzbek work" with the names "cotton work" and "Uzbek work" in this novel. from "political cleansing" to "Afghan war" and its unparalleled sufferings on the people, "Temurs" and "Khayriddins" of the country, who shed blood in a foreign country and became innocent martyrs. The fate of the "Rustams", the difficulties of the "Second World War", the wanderings of the "Repression period" and some "defects" that escalated in the 80s and their consequences reflected the dreams and aspirations of our people, similar to the happiness of having children.

The novel is written with intense pain, and in it we see an artist who has deepened his thinking and matured with social pains. Because the artist saw and felt this environment with his own eyes. In this regard, Critic A. Rasulov comments on the content of the spirit of the work as follows: O. Hoshimov did not limit himself to the description of the character of people in "Dreams of Lives." As in the time of the Shura, it is impossible to reflect this, there is no longer the pressure of unwritten laws that it is necessary to illuminate a person's social essence." The artist follows his own philosophical path in choosing the names of the characters in this work. For example: He devoted his whole life to serving the state of the Shuras, turned the nation's children into "alien elements" with his own hands, is suspicious of his wife and his own child when the time comes, and is alien to the concept of religion and nation. Anievich will turn into an "unnecessary object" in time.

It is as if the writer tells us that Saat is "time", Ganievich is "booty", "no matter

how much oppression is fleeting, only goodness remains in this world". The novel portrays real-life scenes by gathering Rustam, his beloved wife Shahnoza, and Rustam's parents into the main plot line. The play begins with the death of Rustam. In the course of the events, the writer reveals the essence of the system that caused the "rustamlar" tragedy while determining the details of the main character's death. It skillfully shows that the human child has no dignity and that their fate is decided in the hands of the commissars who created the system.

It seems illogical for a brave young man like Rustam to choose death and commit suicide in the prime of his youth. But if you think about it carefully, the Afghan war, its thousands of innocent victims, and the repression of the people under the pretext of "Uzbek affairs" are illogical. Rustam is a victim of this irrationality. The writer himself says in this regard: "Those were the times when the Shura era was over. On the one hand, there is an Afghan war. On the other hand, under the pretext of "Uzbek affairs", our people are playing with the sword of repression. "Iron coffins" of our young soldiers arrive one day from Afghanistan and one day from inside the country. It's like a nightmare..." The name of the novel was not chosen for nothing. Adib refers to the social and spiritual condition of the nation, which has been in a state of slumber for 70 years and lived in sleep. In the play, Rustam's father, who lived faithfully to the communist covenant for many years, says in a letter to his son after being imprisoned for slander: "When I think about it, my past life is not a life, but a dream.

It was as if I was dreaming that someone had taken sleeping pills without realizing it: sometimes I had a sweet dream, sometimes a dangerous one, and I followed wherever that "someone" dragged me... and I waited until I woke up. "I was tired... and now, when I wake up and look around, there are many people like me...". These words apply not only to the chairman who saw the injustices of the system he lived in and suffered unfairly, but also to all the characters of the novel, and thousands of victims in their person. When they wake up from this nightmare, they are convinced that the ideas they believed in are in vain, and what they believed in

for a lifetime has become a mirage. Novels, short stories, and stories also contained the eternal main problem of the art of words - the artistic analysis of human destiny and soul. In many places, the author artistically expressed the extremely elegant processes in the psyche of the characters, along with the interpretation of current social problems.

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